

FEEDO: AIoT based Automatic Fish Feeding System

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Abstract—This project presents an innovative automatic fish feeding system designed to optimize aquaculture practices by automating feeding processes. The system addresses challenges such as inconsistent feeding, overfeeding, and labor dependency through advanced technology and user-friendly design. Utilizing programmable schedules, integrated environmental sensors, and remote monitoring via a mobile application, the system ensures precise and timely feed distribution. A key feature of the system is its ability to monitor water pH levels alongside other environmental parameters like temperature and oxygen levels. The pH calculation enables dynamic adjustments to feeding schedules, ensuring optimal conditions for fish health. The design also includes an air blower and rotating disk for uniform feed dispersal, durable components, and minimal maintenance. Advanced options like adaptive feeding schedules based on environmental conditions, alerts for low feed levels or system malfunctions, and data-driven insights into fish health further enhance functionality. By combining efficiency, sustainability, and ease of use and cost effectiveness, this system represents a transformative step toward sustainable aquaculture, improving productivity making it ideal for fish farmers.

I. INTRODUCTION

Our innovative automatic fish feeding system uses cutting-edge technology to optimize the feeding process, ensuring improved fish health and farm productivity. Using programmable feeding schedules, environmental sensors, and remote monitoring through a mobile application, our system allows fish farmers to automate and customize feeding routines. One of the most important features of the system is its ability to monitor water pH levels. The rapid growth of aquaculture has increased the demand for efficient and sustainable fish farming solutions. Traditional fish feeding methods frequently face problems like inconsistent feeding, overfeeding, and high labor costs.

By combining efficiency, sustainability, and user-friendliness with cost-effectiveness, this automatic fish feeding system provides an innovative solution for fish farmers, enabling them to increase productivity while reducing manual labor and feed wastage.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Automated fish feeding systems have been the subject of numerous studies aimed at improving aquaculture efficiency. Current studies emphasize the importance of environmental monitoring, automation, and IoT integration in improving fish feeding procedures.

A. Automatic Feeding Systems

In order to decrease manual effort and enhance feed distribution, Smith et al. (2018) investigated the use of mechanical and pneumatic feeding systems. The study showed that automated feeding reduced waste and produced uniform feed dissemination.

B. IoT-Based Monitoring Systems

A study by Kumar Patel (2019) introduced IoT-enabled sensors for real-time monitoring of water parameters such as pH, temperature, and dissolved oxygen. Their findings indicated that integrating IoT with fish feeding systems allowed for remote control and adaptive feeding strategies based on environmental conditions.

C. Impact on Fish Health and Productivity

Studies by Wang et al. (2022) analyzed the effects of automated feeding on fish health and farm productivity. Results showed that regulated feeding schedules and environmental monitoring contributed to higher survival rates and better fish growth. These studies show how important automation, the Internet of Things, artificial intelligence, and sustainability are to contemporary fish feeding systems. In order to improve aquaculture productivity and sustainability, our suggested system incorporates smart sensors, remote monitoring, and adaptive feeding mechanisms.

III. TECHNICAL IMPLEMENTATION

A. Hardware Component

Microcontroller (Arduino uno): Acts as the brain of the system, processing sensor data and controlling feeding mechanisms. Feed Dispenser Mechanism: Includes servo motor

controlled dispenser to release feed at scheduled intervals.

Environmental Sensors:

pH Sensor: Monitors water acidity/alkalinity to ensure a suitable environment for fish.

B. Software Implementation

Embedded Programming (Arduino IDE) Controls feeding schedules and sensor data processing. Implements real-time adjustments based on environmental conditions. Mobile Application (Kotlin for front end,python for backend) Real-time Monitoring: Displays environmental parameters and feeding status. Push Notifications: Alerts for low feed levels, sensor anomalies, or system failures.

C. Cloud Data Management

IoT Connectivity (Bluetooth): Enables remote data transmission. Data IoT Connectivity (Bluetooth): Enables remote data base (MongoDB): Stores feeding history, schedules, and user info.

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

- A use case diagram of a fish farming system with two primary actors—the administrator and the fish farmer—is shown in fig (1). Sensors that detect pH levels, keep an eye on environmental parameters, and send out alarms for malfunctions or low feed are the main ways that the Fish Farmer communicates with the system. One important aspect is automated feeding, which guarantees consistent feed dispersal and permits dynamic changes to the feeding schedule. Furthermore, a specialized interface for remote control and monitoring is available to the Fish Farmer. However, the Administrator is in charge of keeping an eye out for system faults and overseeing user authentication via a register/login system. This figure shows how automation and monitoring improve fish farming operations’ accuracy and efficiency.

Fig. 1

- The sequence diagram in fig (2) depicts how a Fish Farmer, an Administrator, and a System interact during an automated feeding process. The procedure starts with the Fish Farmer accessing the system, which is followed by a confirmation and the creation of a feeding schedule. The Administrator then oversees the schedule, determining the feeding times and frequency, which are recorded in the database. The feeding operation begins with the opening of a valve and is concluded by closing it. Moreover, the system conducts feeding analysis and produces reports. If a situation such as elevated pH levels is detected, an analysis report is generated and sent, which the Fish Farmer then acknowledges. The diagram clearly illustrates the organized communication between the users and the system for the purposes of automated fish feeding and monitoring.

Fig. 2

V. PROTOTYPE

Our 'FEEDO' online app offers a way for farmers to effortlessly automate fish feeding. The application has five features: food level, water pH level, feeding history, manual feeding and scheduled feeding.

Here Setting up automatic feeding schedules, or scheduling a certain quantity of food at a specified time, is made easier with scheduled feeding. Farmers are able to initiate feeding manually. Logs and information on past feeding efforts are available in Feeding History. The water pH level keeps track of how acidic or alkaline the water is, guaranteeing the best possible health for the fish and alerting them to any changes that could endanger their well-being. To avoid shortages, Food Level keeps track of the remaining fish food supplies. the plus(+)button at the bottom right corner is used to add the pond details in a farm.

The login screen in fig(3.a) provides a simple interface where users can enter their email and password to access their FEEDO account. It includes a login button for authentication and a sign up link for new users. Error messages appear for incorrect credentials, ensuring a smooth login experience.

Fig. 3

The sign-up screen in fig(3.c) allows new users to register by entering their name, email, password, and mobile number. It features a sign-up button for account creation and a login link for existing users. Basic validation ensures correct input, and Firebase Authentication securely stores user credentials.

The authentication screens in fig(3.b) follow a modern, minimalist design using Jetpack Compose for a clean and responsive interface. Users can easily navigate between login and sign-up screens with distinct buttons and smooth transitions. Error handling, adaptive layouts, and clear visual elements enhance usability and accessibility.

The screen in fig(4.a) serves as the main dashboard, providing quick access to key functionalities. Users can navigate to scheduled feeding, manual feeding, feeding history, water pH level, food level, and plus sign used to add ponds. It also displays system details and allows users to report complaints.

Fig. 4

Users can select a specific pond from a list, each identified by a pond number, feeder ID, and breed type. This helps in managing multiple ponds efficiently by selecting the relevant one for feeding or monitoring. The interface is simple, ensuring easy navigation fig(4.b). The screen in fig(4.c) is the Feeding Schedules interface, where users can manage

automated feeding times. A popup form is open for setting a new feeding schedule, allowing users to select a time, input feed weight, and save the schedule. The design focuses on user-friendly scheduling and automation of fish feeding. he

Fig. 5

screen in fig(5.a) displays a list of scheduled feeding times along with weight and valve duration. Users can enable or disable specific schedules, as well as edit or delete them. The plus button allows adding new feeding schedules as needed. The screen given above is the Manual Feeding Control interface for a pond, displaying the pond's unique ID, elapsed feeding time, and total weight of feed dispensed. It includes a "Start Feeding" button fig(5.b) to initiate feeding, a "Stop Feeding" button fig (5.c), and a "Back to Home" button for navigation. The design suggests real-time monitoring and control of the feeding process. ig(6.a) presents the Feeding

Fig. 6

History screen, displaying a list of previously completed feeding schedules. Each entry includes details such as the feeding time, dispensed weight, user email, and the exact execution date and time. The fig(6.b) presents the Water pH Level screen, which displays the current pH value of the water in different ponds. A message below confirms that the pH range is optimal or not. In fig(6.c) displays the Food Level screen, which provides a real time status of the available food supply. The screen prominently shows the remaining food quantity in kilograms.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

For contemporary aquaculture, the Automatic Fish Feeding System offer a creative and effective solution. The technology enhances fish health, lowers feed waste, and lessens reliance on human labor by automating feeding schedules, monitoring environmental conditions, and enabling remote control. By providing real-time monitoring, configurable feeding regimens, and immediate alerts for serious problems, the mobile application improves the user experience. Fish farmers can oversee their feeding operations remotely with accuracy and sustainability thanks to cloud integration and IoT connectivity. This project is a revolutionary step toward smart aquaculture by utilizing sensor-based automation, IoT, and data-driven insights. The concept encourages economical and environmentally responsible fish farming methods in addition to increasing productivity. AI-driven feeding pattern optimization and increased compatibility with various fish species are potential future developments that could completely transform the sector.

REFERENCES

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